

Optimizing Postal Delivery and Waste Collection Using Electric Vehicles

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Abstract—This paper presents an Electric Vehicle Routing problem specified in the case of Postal Delivery and Waste Collection activities. The problems are formulated as Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problems with the objective of carrying out the collection or delivery activities by minimizing the route length, respecting the time and Electric Vehicles (EVs) battery charge constraints. While satisfying the customer needs under the mentioned travel constraints, the proposed models take into account the implementation of smart charging strategies to minimize the demand peaks on the power grid both at district and charge station levels, that is suitable in large scale problems. To address the complexity of the models, a heuristic algorithm based on clustering and routing strategies is proposed. Two case studies are implemented to demonstrate the effectiveness of the models for Postal Delivery and Waste Collection activities in large systems.

Index Terms—Electric Vehicles, Smart Charging, Postal Delivery, Waste Collection

I. INTRODUCTION

THE problem of routing a fleet of vehicles that have to accomplish last-mile delivery tasks still need attention of researchers and practitioners to find innovative solutions minimizing the travel costs and optimizing the service quality. The increasing availability of Information and Communication Technologies allows the development of new models and strategies to optimize the information and the service management for the urban decision makers [1].

Among the most critical logistic services to be managed in the smart cities, the Postal Delivery (PD) and Waste Collection (WC) services are considered crucial in the urban logistics. These services are essential for citizens and can impact both on the urban traffic and environment. In postal delivery, the main problem is to optimize the route of the company fleet serving the customers network, minimizing travel cost, respecting time constraints and ensuring a high quality service [1].

The WC routing problem is another critical management issue to be solved in order to guarantee an efficient and fast WC service [1]. It consists in designing the optimal routes to be traveled by a fleet of vehicles with limited cargo capacities to serve a set of customers.

For last-mile delivery services and in particular for PD and WC services, EVs started to be used in order to reduce the environmental impact of conventional PD vehicles and WC trucks. The benefits of using electric vehicle fleet in urban logistics applications has been largely demonstrated [10].

In this work, we study both the PD and WC problems to be solved efficiently by using EVs. EVs show an effective and attractive driving and their travels have zero impact on the environment. On the contrary, the EVs still show some drawbacks in most of cases, regarding the limited driving range and the long charging times. For these reasons, in order to be used in long distance/time trips they may need to be recharged at specific charging points [11]. The charging infrastructure for EVs is today even more diffusing across the countries and many charging points (CPs) are available today both in urban and extra-urban areas. Nevertheless, fast direct current CPs are still limited in number, but many investments and projects are ongoing to increase their availability.

This paper solves the PD and WC problems using EVs and modelling the system as an Electric Vehicle Routing Problem (EVRP). The EVRP is an extension of the Vehicle Routing Problem and it deals with providing effective route plans for EVs minimizing a cost function while satisfying a set of battery-related constraints and charging operations [15]. The objective function can be based on the minimization of travel distance or time, total charging demand, time and cost, total energy consumption, number of EVs or CPs used and other operational costs [12], [15]. In general, the main assumptions in a EVRP are the following: each route starts and ends at the depot node; each customer node is to be served by one EV; EVs can visit a CP for charging operations between any two customers; each CP can be visited by more than one EV; the locations of the CPs and the traveling distance from any node to any CP are known; the SoC of an EV must always be between a minimum SoC level and its battery capacity [15].

Moreover, to deal with the routing problem of EVs in PD and WC operations it is necessary to take into account the EV charging operations. In this work, we take care about the power grid load due to the EV charging demand. Indeed, to avoid peak of demand on the grid, smart charging strategies are applied in order to preserve the grid and to exploit also the use of renewable energies where present. To this purpose, the EV charging operation can be temporarily interrupted at the CP in order to mitigate the grid load peak and discharging operations through the Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology [13], [14]). The discharging operations are implemented to feed energy back to the main grid alleviating the grid and providing it with some extra-energy that can be used for other scopes (storage, charging other EV batteries with lower State of Charge (SoC)).

The contribution of the paper can be summarized as follows.

- This work focuses on the routing of EVs for PD and WC services considering EVs, on the contrary paper

[1] uses internal combustion engine vehicles. Indeed, EVs have different technology and consumption model from internal combustion engine vehicles, a more limited driving range and long recharging time. Therefore, new models are needed to manage EVs travels and charging operations.

- With respect to the contributions on the EV routing problem, this paper proposes solutions taking into account the grid load peaks through smart charging strategies based on V2G technology.
- The EVRP is formalized and solved as Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem. Since the EVRP is known to be NP-hard [27], [1], it can be solved in reasonable time only if the dimension of the system is limited. Hence, we propose a heuristic algorithm based on clustering and routing strategies to be applied in real case studies.
- Two realistic case studies are presented, one for PD services and one for WC services, to demonstrate the use of the proposed approach and evaluate the real performances and potentialities.

The remaining part of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the related works focusing mainly on the EVRP literature contributions, Section III describes the EVRP for WC and PD. In addition, Section IV proposes the mathematical formulations of the two optimization models for PD and WC problems. Section V describes the heuristic strategy for node clustering and EV routing. Finally, Section VI and Section VII discuss two different case studies solving real PD and WC problems, respectively, and Section VIII concludes the work.

II. RELATED WORKS

The EVRP has been studied with different variants by researchers which include multiple types of CPs, multiple depots, heterogeneous EVs, time windows, energy consumption uncertainty and nonlinear charging functions [16].

In [17], the authors study an EVRP with different technologies and charging strategies. The proposed EVRP considers various types of CPs and allows dynamic charging operations and partial recharging. Each type of CP has a given recharge cost and speed and the objective is to minimize the total recharging cost, given by a fixed cost and a variable cost proportional to the amount of energy recharged. Three heuristics are applied showing that they are competitive with the state of the art.

Lin et al. [18] present a general EVRP with the objective of minimizing the total cost, i.e. the battery charging cost, travel time cost, and battery-charging waiting time cost. The EVRP is formulated as a MILP model and solve it using Matlab. A limited battery capacity and unrestricted charging activities at CPs are considered. They also demonstrate in a case study that the battery consumption is affected by the EV cargo load.

In addition, Granada-Echeverri et al. [19] introduce the EVRP with backhauls and formulate the problem as a MILP model. This formulation based on the classic EVRP considers a set of new constraints focused on satisfying the condition

of the linehaul (products to be delivered to customers) and backhaul (products to be picked-up from the customers and delivered to the depot) paths. Different CPs are considered in order to recharge the EV battery at the end of the linehaul route or during the backhaul route. An iterated local search algorithm is designed for obtaining a feasible integer solution of the problem in a fast time. The backhaul as well as the charging operations are also considered in [20] in which the authors aim at generating a set of vehicle routes that are consistent with driver and time requirements and make an efficient use of the limited charging resources, optimizing the sum of vehicle fixed cost, vehicle/driver operating time and arrival time. Other authors deal with the uncertainty of the energy consumed during the trip by the EVs like in [21]. In [21], a stochastic problem is formulated starting from a deterministic MIP model for minimizing the total fixed cost of EVs, the total maintenance cost proportional to the total traveling distance, and worst-case energy cost. Other authors like for instance in [22], [23], include also the uncertainty and dynamicity of the customers demand.

With particular reference with the multi-compartment delivery problem, in [25] the multi-compartment EVRP with soft time window and multiple charging types is studied, in which EV charging problem is considered. A mathematical model of the problem is established with the objective of minimizing the function composed of vehicle cost, distribution cost, time window penalty cost and charging service cost. Using electric multi-compartment vehicles to deliver incompatible products can produce better results than using traditional fuel vehicles.

In [26] the authors study the EVRP with flexible deliveries. In this problem, a customer may specify different delivery locations for different time windows. The objective is to serve the customers while minimizing the total travelled distance using minimum number of vehicles. The problem is modeled and solved through a hybrid Variable Neighbourhood Search coupled with Tabu Search. The experimental results exhibited 25% reduction in fleet size and 49% reduction in fuel cost, and revealed that the operational costs can be cut down significantly if the logistics operators collaborate with energy companies.

The work in [27] presents a Multi-Depot EVRP with CPs by considering the expected penalty of fuzzy time windows in pickup/delivery. Since it is an NP-hard problem, three meta-heuristics (i.e., Simulated Annealing (SA), Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) and a hybrid of SA and VNS that shows the best performance) are used to solve such a problem. A multi-depot EVRP is also studied in [28] considering battery recharging and swapping in last-mile delivery. In addition, other works apply reinforcement learning [29] and deep reinforcement learning [30] for solving the EVRP not only for logistics and transportation company but also for ride hailing services.

In [1], the authors propose a two-phase heuristic algorithm based on a clustering strategy and a farthest insertion heuristic for the solution of a VAR problem. The proposed heuristic algorithm solutions are compared with the MILP problem solutions of the PD and WC services.

We enlighten that in the related literature the important

limitations of the power grid peaks are not considered, a problem that can be addressed by the smart charge approaches able to considering the possibility of charging and discharging the EVs. This paper aims to deal with this gap by defining new EVRPs including this feature.

III. ELECTRIC VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEM

This section describes the EVRP for WC and PD problems. In particular, we study the routing problem of a fleet of EVs that have to serve a set of customers taking into account cargo capacity, battery SoC, power grid energy peaks and time constraints. In this scenario, the main objective is to minimize the total length of the EVs travelled routes.

In the PD tasks, the EVs depart from the depot, make the deliveries to customers, and then return to the depot. In the case of WC, the EV departs from the depot, collects waste at various points, and when the EV's cargo capacity reaches its maximum, the EV goes to the landfill. Note that the main difference is that in the WC multiple routes are performed by the same EV.

Moreover, EVs have a maximum cargo capacity and a maximum battery capacity that are taken into account during travel. To maintain power grid reliability, smart charging and discharging are implemented considering energy consumption models and energy supply price strategies.

A. Nomenclature

This subsection lists the parameters and notations used in the paper:

\mathcal{A}	Set of arcs with $A = \mathcal{A} $ and $ \cdot $ stands for cardinality of set (\cdot)
\mathcal{K}	Set of EVs with $K = \mathcal{K} $
\mathcal{K}^u	Set of used EVs $K^u \subseteq \mathcal{K}$
\mathcal{K}^{Nu}	Set of not used EVs $K^{Nu} \subseteq \mathcal{K}$
$\tilde{\mathcal{N}}$	Set of Customers with $\tilde{N} = \tilde{\mathcal{N}} $
\mathcal{N}^S	Set of served nodes $N^S \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$
\mathcal{N}^{NS}	Set of not served nodes $N^{NS} \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$
\mathcal{N}'	Set of CPs that are also customers with $N' = \mathcal{N}' $
$\hat{\mathcal{N}}$	Set of CPs with $\hat{N} = \hat{\mathcal{N}} $
\mathcal{N}	Set of Nodes with $N = \mathcal{N} $
\mathcal{P}	Set of Districts with $P = \mathcal{P} $
\mathcal{T}	Set of Time slots with $T = \mathcal{T} $
P^k	District used during the EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ trip
$U - 1$	Number of customers
Z	Number of CPs
Y	Number of districts
d_i	Demand of customer $n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ [kg]
p_i	Service duration at customer $n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ [minutes]
C^k	Cargo capacity of vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ [kg]
$C_{i,j}^k$	Cargo load of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ traveling from n_i to n_j , $n_i, n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ [kg]
Q^k	Battery capacity of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ [kWh]
Q_i^k	Current SoC of battery of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ [kWh]
Q_L^k	Minimum allowed SoC of battery of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ [kWh]

W_i^k	Starting time of the action (PD or WC) of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at node $n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ [minutes]
W^k	Working time of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ [minutes]
m	Route index of each EV trip
td_{ij}	Distance to travel from n_i to n_j , $n_i, n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ [km]
$Ttd^k(t)$	Total travel distance of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ [km]
tt_{ij}	Time to travel from n_i to n_j , $n_i, n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ [minutes]
T_r	Maximum route time of each EV [minutes]
T_w	Maximum working time of each EV [minutes]
\mathcal{N}_m^k	Set of nodes visited in route m of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ trip
$\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_m^k$	Gives ordered visited nodes by EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ during the m th route
L_m^k	Total cargo load of $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_m^k$ [kg]
B_m^k	Duration of route $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_m^k$ [minutes]
\hat{B}^k	Duration of the EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ trip [minutes]
$open_i$	Open hour to start service allowed at node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ [h]
$close_i$	Close hour to finish service at node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ [h]
c_k	Energy consumption of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ for every 100 km traveled [kWh/100km]
$power_i(t)$	Power that CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ can provide at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ [kW]
$e_i(t)$	Energy provided by CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}$ at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ [kWh]
$ed_p(t)$	Energy provided by district $p \in \mathcal{P}$ at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ [kWh]
$emax_i(t)$	Maximum energy that CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ can provide in each time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ [kW]
$emax_p(t)$	Maximum energy that district $p \in \mathcal{P}$ can provide in each time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ [kW]
$temp_i$	Outdoor temperature at node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ [$^{\circ}C$]
$cost(t)$	Cost of charging at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ [€/kW]
$tCost_i^k$	Travel cost of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ [€/kW]
$r_i^k(t)$	Binary decision variable equal to 1 if EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ charges its battery at CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$
$d_i^k(t)$	Binary decision variable equal to 1 if EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ discharges its battery at CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}$ at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$
$x_{i,j}^k$	Binary decision variable equal to 1 if EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ travels from node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ to node $n_j \in \mathcal{N}$
s_i^p	Binary parameter equal to 1 if CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ belongs to district $p \in \mathcal{P}$

B. Electric Vehicle Routing Problem Description

We consider a fleet of \mathcal{K} EVs that have the mission of carrying out waste collection or postal delivery activities. Each EV has a cargo capacity [Kg] denoted by C^k for EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$. In addition, the maximum battery capacity [kWh] of the EVs (e.g. Q^k for EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$) must be taken into account in order to manage the charging operations. Moreover, the following sets and elements are defined:

- $\tilde{\mathcal{N}} = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{U-1}\}$ is the set of customers n_i for $i = 1, \dots, n_{U-1}$;
- n_0 is the initial depot node;
- n_U is the final depot node that represents also the end node of the routes;
- $\mathcal{N}' = \{n_{U+1}, \dots, n_V\}$ is the set of CPs that are also customers;
- $\tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ is the set of n_V customer nodes;
- $\hat{\mathcal{N}} = \{n_{V+1}, \dots, n_Z\}$ is the set of CPs that are not considered customers;
- $\hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ is the set of CPs;
- $\mathcal{P} = \{p | p = 1, \dots, Y\}$ is the set of Y districts. Note that each CP node $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}$ belongs to an energy district $p \in \mathcal{P}$;
- $s_i^p \in \{0, 1\}$ and $s_i^p = 1$ if CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ belongs to district $p \in \mathcal{P}$.

We also define the maximum energy peak $emax_i(t)$ to be respected for each CP $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ in the time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ and we denote the maximum energy peak by $emax_p(t)$ for the district $p \in \mathcal{P}$ to be respected in each time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

The network of customers and CPs is modeled by a fully connected directed graph $G = \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A}\}$, where \mathcal{N} is the set of nodes and \mathcal{A} is the set of arcs. More precisely, it holds $\mathcal{N} = \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \{n_0\} \cup \{n_U\} \cup \mathcal{N}' \cup \hat{\mathcal{N}}$, i.e., the set of nodes \mathcal{N} includes the customers, the charging points and the depots. Moreover, an arc $a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}$ if there is a directed connection between nodes i and j .

The EV fleet travels through the graph nodes serving customers with pick-up or delivery operations. During the travel, in each of the customer nodes, EVs can carry out delivery or collection operations and they can charge or discharge (in case of smart charging application) the battery in CP nodes. Each route starts from the depot node n_0 and, when the EV reaches the cargo capacity or time limit, or has no possibility of charging, it is redirected to the depot (end node) n_U . EVs must respect a traveling time constraint T_r [minutes] on each route m they make, and it cannot exceed the maximum work time T_w [minutes].

Each node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ is characterized by the following parameters:

- an opening hour to start the postal or waste collection service lower than the closing hour $open_i < close_i$;
- the outdoor temperature $temp_i$ at node i , important to estimate the EV consumption including the use of the air conditioning system;
- each customer node $n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ has a demand $d_i \geq 0 \in \mathbb{R}$ and a service duration $p_i \geq 0 \in \mathbb{R}$. If, $d_i = p_i = 0$ the node $n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ is not to be served;
- each CP node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}' \cup \hat{\mathcal{N}}$ can provide the charging power $power_i(t)$ in time slot t ;
- the charging power must not exceed the maximum energy $emax_i(t)$ in each time slot.

To each arc a_{ij} connecting node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ with node $n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ the labels td_{ij} and tt_{ij} are associated to denote the travel distance and the travel time between the two nodes, respectively.

Let us define the set \mathcal{N}_m^k containing the customer nodes and CP nodes visited in route m of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Now, we

assign to the route m of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ the function $\check{N}_m^k : N \rightarrow \mathcal{N}_m^k \cup \{n_0, n_U\}$, where N stands for the set of natural numbers. More precisely, $\check{N}_m^k(j) = n_i$ means that in the m th route of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $n_i \in \mathcal{N}_m^k \cup \{n_0, n_U\}$ is the j th visited node, with $j = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{N}_m^k| + 2$. The depot node is $\check{N}_m^k(1) \in \{n_0, n_U\}$ and the last node of the route is $\check{N}_m^k(|\mathcal{N}_m^k| + 2) \in \{n_0, n_U\}$.

Moreover, $\check{N}_m^k(j)$ can be a customer node visited exactly once, or a CP node. We denote with \bar{j} the total number of visited nodes and with $\bar{m} \geq 2$ the last route in the EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ trip. The following conditions for function $\check{N}_m^k(j)$ are imposed:

$$\begin{aligned} \check{N}_m^k(j) &= n_0 \quad \text{if } m = 1 \text{ and } j = 1 \\ \check{N}_m^k(j) &= n_0 \quad \text{if } m = \bar{m} \text{ and } j = \bar{j}; \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \check{N}_m^k(j) &= n_U \quad \text{if } 1 \leq m < \bar{m}, j = \bar{j} \\ \check{N}_m^k(j) &= n_U \quad \text{if } 1 < m \leq \bar{m}, j = \bar{j}; \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

i.e., each EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ departs in the first route from the depot and returns to the depot in the last route.

Conditions (2) constraint each route to end at n_U and start from n_U except the last route in the first case ($1 \leq m < \bar{m}$, $j = \bar{j}$) and the first route in the second case ($1 < m \leq \bar{m}$, $j = \bar{j}$). For all the other cases $n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ is considered.

The number of routes performed by each EV is $\bar{m} \leq M$, with M maximum number of routes for EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$. The following equation defines B_m^k that represents the total time duration of the route m defined by \check{N}_m^k :

$$B_m^k = \sum_{j=1}^{\bar{j}-1} \left(p_{\check{N}_m^k(j)} + tt_{\check{N}_m^k(j), \check{N}_m^k(j+1)} \right). \quad (3)$$

Note that $B_m^k \leq T_r$ that is the maximum route time T_r of each $k \in \mathcal{K}$.

In addition, L_m^k [Kg] denotes the total cargo load of the EV k at the end of the route m :

$$L_m^k = \sum_{j=1}^{\bar{j}} d_{\check{N}_m^k(j)}. \quad (4)$$

A route m is defined *feasible* if it holds $L_m^k \leq C^k$.

Finally, \hat{B}^k is the total duration of the \bar{m} routes of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$, that must be less than or equal to T_w :

$$\hat{B}^k = \sum_{i=1}^{\bar{m}} B_i^k + tt_{U,0} \leq T_w. \quad (5)$$

The criteria followed to assign the EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ to each of the routes is related to its cargo capacity C^k : EVs are ordered and assigned on the basis of the cargo capacity in descending order.

C. Decision Variables

The decision variables of the EVRP are the following:

- $r_i^k(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ and $r_i^k(t) = 1$ if EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ charges its battery at CP $n_i \in \mathcal{N}' \cup \hat{\mathcal{N}}$ at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$
- $d_i^k(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ and $d_i^k(t) = 1$ if EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ discharges its battery at CP $n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$ at time slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$
- $x_{i,j}^k \in \{0, 1\}$ and $x_{i,j}^k = 1$ if EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ travels from node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ to node $n_j \in \mathcal{N}$.

D. Energy Consumption Model

The energy consumption model of an EV depends on the traveled distance, the cargo load, the use of the air conditioning system and the weather conditions.

The energy consumption of the EV battery is determined for every 100 km traveled and is computed as follows:

$$dc_{i,j}^k = td_{i,j} \cdot c_k \quad (6)$$

where $dc_{i,j}^k$ is the travel distance-based consumption of the EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ and c_k [kWh/100km] is the energy demand per 100km. The energy consumption $wc_{i,j}^k$ depends on the cargo load of the EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$. According to [34], increasing the EV mass by 100 kg leads to increasing the energy consumption by 0.34 kWh/100 km. Based on that, we can calculate the energy consumption from $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ to $n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ by:

$$wc_{i,j}^k = td_{i,j} \cdot 0.34 \cdot C_{i,j}^k. \quad (7)$$

Moreover, $tc_{i,j}^k$ denotes the part of energy consumption depending on the use of the heating/cooling system for EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$. This energy demand denoted by $ta_{i,j}$ is calculated taking into account the outdoor average temperature of nodes $n_i, n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ as follows:

$$ta_{i,j} = \frac{temp_i + temp_j}{2}. \quad (8)$$

If $ta_{i,j} \leq 18^\circ C$ and if $ta_{i,j} \geq 25^\circ C$, then the heating system is considered on. According to the study in [35], activating the heating system increases the energy consumption of 18%, while using the cooling system, the energy consumption increases of 14%:

$$tc_{i,j}^k = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 18^\circ C < ta_{i,j} < 25^\circ C \\ 0.18 \cdot dc_{i,j}^k & \text{if } ta_{i,j} \leq 18^\circ C \\ 0.14 \cdot dc_{i,j}^k & \text{if } ta_{i,j} \geq 25^\circ C. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Thus, the total energy consumption $c_{i,j}^k$ of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ traveling from node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ to node $n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ is calculated as follows:

$$c_{i,j}^k = dc_{i,j}^k + wc_{i,j}^k + tc_{i,j}^k. \quad (10)$$

E. Charge and Discharge Time-Variant Pricing

In this section, we present the dynamic pricing strategy adopted for charging and discharging operations. In particular, a Real-Time Pricing (RTP) method is proposed to determine the energy tariff to be applied in each time slot.

The proposed RTP is designed to avoid the peak of demand on the power grid both at CP and at district level. A measure has been adopted in which the price varies based on the energy level reached by both the CP and the district. In detail, a two-slot RTP strategy is implemented: 1) if the peak of energy demand on the CP is greater than 80% of the $emax_i(t)$, or if the peak of energy demand on the district is greater than 80% of the $emax_p(t)$ during the charging, then the applied tariff is $cost_{c1}(t)$; 2) otherwise, if the used energy level is under 80% of the $emax_i(t)/emax_p(t)$, then the applied tariff is $cost_{c2}(t)$. The $cost_{c1}(t)$ must be greater than $cost_{c2}(t)$.

In case of discharging, the $cost_d(t)$ is considered. The applied tariff in any case is $cost_d(t) \leq cost_{c2}(t)$.

IV. ELECTRIC VEHICLE ASSIGNMENT AND ROUTING OPTIMIZATION MODELS

A. Postal Delivery Problem

The main activity of the PD system is the distribution of the postal products from the depot node to the customer nodes.

The postal network is modeled by a fully connected directed graph G formed by depot node, customer nodes and CP nodes. The delivery service is performed by a single route ($M = 1$) in which each EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$ starts from and ends to the depot node.

B. Postal Delivery Mathematical Formulation

In this section, we present the MILP modeling the PD problem. Please note that to simplify the formulation layout, the time dependence (t) is omitted.

$$\min \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \sum_{i,j:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} td_{ij} \cdot x_{ij}^k \quad (11)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \sum_{i,j:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij}^k = 1 \quad \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N} \cup \mathcal{N}' \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{i,j:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{j:a_{0j} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{0j}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{i:a_{iU} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{iU}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{i:a_{i0} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{i0}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{i:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij}^k - \sum_{j:a_{ji} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ji}^k = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_j \in \mathcal{N}$$

$$x_{ij}^k = 1 \Rightarrow L_j^k = L_i^k + d_j \quad (18)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}$$

$$W_j^k \geq W_i^k + p_i + tt_{ij} \quad (19)$$

$$x_{ij}^k = 1, r_i^k = 0, d_i^k = 0$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}$$

$$W_j^k \geq W_i^k + p_i + \frac{((Q_i^k - Q_i^k) \cdot r_i^k) \cdot 60}{power_{i,t}} + tt_{ij} \quad (20)$$

$$x_{ij}^k = 1, r_i^k = 1, d_i^k = 0, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$$

$$\forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$$

$$W_j^k \geq W_i^k + p_i + \frac{((Q_i^k - 0.10 \cdot Q_i^k) \cdot d_i^k) \cdot 60}{power_{i,t}} + tt_{ij} \quad (21)$$

$$x_{ij}^k = 1, r_i^k = 0, d_i^k = 1, \forall k \in \mathcal{K},$$

$$\forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$$

$$0 \leq W_{\bar{N}}^k \leq T_w \quad (22)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$$

$$0 \leq L_i^k \leq C^k \quad (23)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K x_{ij}^k \cdot e_i \leq \text{emax}_i \quad (24)$$

$$\forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K x_{ij}^k \cdot \text{ed}_p \cdot s_i^p \leq \text{emax}_p \quad (25)$$

$$\forall p \in \mathcal{P}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$$

$$r_i^k + d_i^k \leq 1 \quad (26)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$$

$$Q_j^k \leq Q_i^k - c_{ij}^k \quad (27)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i, n_j \in \bar{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$$

$$r_i^k = 1 \Rightarrow Q_j^k \geq Q_i^k + c_{ij}^k + c_{j,U}^k \quad (28)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i, n_j \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$$

$$d_i^k = 1 \Rightarrow Q_j^k \leq Q_i^k - c_{ij}^k - 0.10 \cdot Q_i^k \quad (29)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \bar{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall n_j \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$$

$$Q_L^k \leq Q_i^k \leq Q^k \quad (30)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}$$

$$r_i^k = 1 \Rightarrow t\text{Cost}_j^k \geq t\text{Cost}_i^k + \text{cost}_c \quad (31)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \bar{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall n_j \in \mathcal{N}$$

$$d_i^k = 1 \Rightarrow t\text{Cost}_j^k \leq t\text{Cost}_i^k - \text{cost}_d(Q^k - Q_i^k) \quad (32)$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \bar{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall n_j \in \mathcal{N}$$

$$x_{ij}^k, r_i^k, d_i^k \in \{0, 1\} \quad (33)$$

The objective function (11) aims to minimize the sum of the routes travelled by the EVs so that they can do the postal delivery using the shortest path and satisfying customer needs. Constraints (12) impose that each customer node is served only once. Constraints (13) impose that for each $k \in \mathcal{K}$, each CP can be visited at most once. Constraints (14) and (15) determine that each EV departs from the depot node n_0 and ends at node $n_U = n_0$. By constraints (16), EVs return to node n_0 after visiting $n_i \in \bar{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$. Constraints (17) assure the flow conservation and constraints (18) update the cargo load value of each EV at each node.

Equations (19) model the arrival time at node n_j by summing up the arrival time at node n_i , the delivery operation

time at node n_i and the traveling time of EV k through the arc $a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}$. In constraints (20), the arrival time at node n_j is determined by summing the arrival time at node n_i , the delivery operation time at node n_i , the charging time at node n_i , and the traveling time of EV k from n_i to n_j . Moreover, in constraints (21), the arrival time at node n_j is computed as in (19) by also taking into account the discharging time of EV k battery at the CP. For both constraints (20) and (21), to match the units of measurement, the battery capacity in kWh is multiplied by 60. Therefore, the unit of measurement for charge and discharge time is also minutes.

Constraints (22) and (23) define the working time and cargo capacity bounds for each EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$, respectively.

Constraints (24) and (25) preserve the power grid avoiding exceeding the maximum allowed energy peak in each CP and district, respectively. Constraints (26) control charging and discharging of EV k battery at CP node $n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$, allowing only one of the two actions to happen at each time t .

Constraints (27), (28), (29) track the battery SoC in three different situations. In constraints (27) the battery SoC is calculated in the case the EV k is traveling. Constraints (28) ensure that in the case the EV battery is charging, it charges until the necessary SoC to reach the next node or/and the destination. Furthermore, in case the battery of EV k is discharging (29), it can be discharged only up to 10% of the current SoC. In this way, a complete discharge of the vehicle is avoided, and it ensures that the vehicle can reach the next node. Constraints (30) impose that the battery SoC of the EV must be between the minimum and maximum SoC.

Constraints (31) and (32) indicate the cost of each EV trip taking into account the battery charging and discharging.

Finally, constraints (33) denote the binary variables.

C. Waste Collection Problem

The main activity of the WC is to collect the waste bin considering different routes. Every day, a fleet of EVs performs the WC subject to time and capacity constraints (cargo and battery). During the day, each EV can perform several routes for a maximum of M .

The first route starts from the depot, picks-up at assigned nodes, and, when the EV is full or the time is attained, it stops at landfill (end node). In this site, the EV unloads the waste and starts a new route from the landfill. The EV ends the trip at depot node by an empty travel from the landfill.

The main objective is to minimize the total length of the routes performed by the EVs.

D. Waste Collection Mathematical Formulation

In this section, we present the MILP modeling the WC problem. Please note that also in this case to simplify the formulation, the time dependence (t) is omitted. The model is very similar tthe PD model, but in WC the m routes of the EV are considered.

$$\min \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{i,j: a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} t d_{ij} \cdot x_{ij,m}^k \quad (34)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \sum_{i,j:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij,m}^k = 1 \quad \forall n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}' \quad (35)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{i,j:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij,m}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (36)$$

$$\sum_{j:a_{0j} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{0j,1}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (37)$$

$$\sum_{m=2}^M \sum_{j:a_{0j,m} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{0j,m}^k = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (38)$$

$$\sum_{j:a_{Uj} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{Uj,m}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, m = 2, \dots, M \quad (39)$$

$$\sum_{j:a_{iU} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{iU,m}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, m = 1, \dots, M \quad (40)$$

$$\sum_{i:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij,m}^k - \sum_{i:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A} - \{a_{j0}\}} x_{ji,m}^k = 0 \quad (41)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_j \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall m$

$$\sum_{i:a_{iU} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{iU,m}^k - \sum_{j:a_{Uj} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{Uj,m+1}^k = 0 \quad (42)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall m = 1, 2, \dots, M-1$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M x_{U0,m}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (43)$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_{j,m}^k &\geq W_{i,m}^k + p_i + tt_{ij} \\ x_{ij}^k &= 1, r_i^k = 0, d_i^k = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall m$

$$\begin{aligned} W_{j,m}^k &\geq W_{i,m}^k + p_i + \frac{((Q^k - Q_{i,m}^k) \cdot r_i^k) \cdot 60}{\text{power}_i} + tt_{ij} \\ x_{ij}^k &= 1, r_i^k = 1, d_i^k = 0, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

$\forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall m$

$$\begin{aligned} W_{j,m}^k &\geq W_{i,m}^k + p_i + \frac{((Q_{i,m}^k - 0.10 \cdot Q_{i,m}^k) \cdot d_i^k) \cdot 60}{\text{power}_i} + tt_{ij} \\ x_{ij}^k &= 1, r_i^k = 0, d_i^k = 1, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

$\forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall m$

$$x_{Uj,m}^k = 1 \Rightarrow L_{j,m}^k = L_{i,m}^k + d_j \quad (47)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A} \text{ s.t. } i \neq U, \forall m$

$$x_{Uj,m}^k = 1 \Rightarrow L_{j,m}^k = d_j \quad (48)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \text{ s.t. } a_{Uj} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall m > 1$

$$0 \leq W_{U,1}^k \leq T_r \quad (49)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$

$$0 \leq W_{U,m}^k - W_{U,m-1}^k - p_U \leq T_r \quad (50)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall m > 1$

$$0 \leq W_{0,m}^k \leq T_w \quad (51)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall m$

$$0 \leq L_{i,m}^k \leq C^k \quad (52)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall m$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} x_{ij,m}^k \cdot e_{i,m} \leq \text{emax}_i \quad (53)$$

$\forall n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall m$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} x_{ij,m}^k \cdot ed_{p,m} \cdot s_i^p \leq \text{emax}_p \quad (54)$$

$\forall p \in \mathcal{P}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall m, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$

$$r_{i,m}^k + d_{i,m}^k \leq 1 \quad (55)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall m$

$$Q_{j,m}^k \leq Q_{i,m}^k - c_{ij}^k \quad (56)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i, n_j \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$

$$r_{i,m}^k = 1 \Rightarrow Q_{j,m}^k \geq Q_{i,m}^k + c_{ij}^k + c_{jU}^k \quad (57)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i, n_j \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall m$

$$d_{i,m}^k = 1 \Rightarrow Q_{j,m}^k \leq Q_{i,m}^k - c_{ij}^k - 0.10 \cdot Q_{i,m}^k \quad (58)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}, \forall n_j \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}, \forall m$

$$Q_L^k \leq Q_{i,m}^k \leq Q^k \quad (59)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}$

$$r_{i,m}^k = 1 \Rightarrow t\text{Cost}_{j,m}^k \geq t\text{Cost}_{i,m}^k + \text{cost}_c \quad (60)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall n_j \in \mathcal{N}, \forall m$

$$d_{i,m}^k = 1 \Rightarrow t\text{Cost}_{j,m}^k \leq t\text{Cost}_{i,m}^k - \text{cost}_d(Q^k - Q_{i,m}^k) \quad (61)$$

$\forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}', \forall n_j \in \mathcal{N}, \forall m$

$$x_{ij,m}^k, r_i^k, d_i^k \in \{0, 1\} \quad (62)$$

The objective function (34) aims to minimize the total length of the travelled routes of the EVs by satisfying customer needs. Constraints (35) impose that each customer node is served only once. Constraints (36) impose that for each $k \in \mathcal{K}$, each CP can be visited at most once. Constraints (37), (38) and (39) determine that each EV departs from the node n_0 at route $m = 1$. Constraints (40) determine that each EV ends at node n_U . Constraints (41) assure the flow conservation.

Constraints (42) connect the end of the m route to the start of the $m+1$ route. Constraints (43) impose that the last route m has to start at node n_U and to end at node n_0 .

Constraints (44) model the arrival time at node n_j by summing up the arrival time at node n_i , the collection operation

time at node n_i and the traveling time of EV k through the arc $a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}$. In constraints (45) the arrival time at node n_j is determined by summing the arrival time at CP n_i , the collection operation time at CP n_i , the charging time at CP n_i , and the traveling time of EV k from CP n_i to node n_j . Moreover, in constraints (46) the arrival time at node n_j is computed as in (44) by also taking into account the discharging time of EV k battery at the CP. For both constraints (45) and (46), to match the units of measurement, the battery capacity in kWh is multiplied by 60. Therefore, the unit of measurement for charge and discharge time is also minutes.

Constraints (47) and (48) update the cargo load of each EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Constraints (49), (50), (51) and (52) define the working time and cargo capacity bounds for each EV k .

Constraints (53) and (54) preserve the power grid to exceeding the maximum allowed energy peak in each CP and district, respectively. Constraints (55) control the charging and discharging of the EV k battery at CP node $n_i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$, allowing only one of the two actions to happen at each time t .

Constraints (56), (57) and (58) track the battery SoC in three different situations. In constraints (56) the battery SoC is calculated in the case EV k is traveling. Constraints (57) ensure that in the case the EV battery is charging, it charges until the necessary SoC to reach the next node or/and the destination. Furthermore, in case the battery of EV k is discharging (58), it can be discharged only up 10% of the current SoC. Equations (59) impose that the battery SoC of the EV must be between the minimum and the maximum SoC.

Constraints (60) and (61) indicate the cost of each EV trip taking into account the charge and discharge of the battery, respectively.

Finally, constraints (62) define the binary decision variables.

V. HEURISTIC STRATEGY FOR NODE CLUSTERING AND EV ROUTING

In this section, an heuristic method is presented that solves the EVRP problems by implementing cluster first, route second approach, a well-established solution for solving the EVRP [11]–[13]. More precisely, a clustering strategy is applied to group customers (i.e., delivery or collection points for PD or WC problems, respectively) and CP nodes and a routing strategy is performed to optimize the routes of EV fleet in each cluster.

Therefore, the proposed method consists on two phases that are applied to each EV trip: 1) the application of the clustering strategy and 2) the application of the routing strategy.

In Phase 1, i.e. in the Clustering Strategy, the EVs are assigned to the clusters on the basis of their cargo capacity (assigned in descending order of cargo capacity). We also assume that the EVs serving the customer nodes in the selected cluster, charge/discharge in CP nodes belonging to the same district. For the latter, the possibility of charging at one of the CPs is taken into account if necessary. In that case, the CP and district peaks are also checked. The population of the cluster is carried out in the following way: the furthest node from the depot node is searched and, from this node, the closest nodes

that have not yet been served are added, until the maximum cargo capacity of the EV is reached, always taking into account the battery constraints.

In Phase 2, the Routing Strategy is carried out. For all the nodes obtained in Phase 1, time constraints T_r and T_w fulfillment is checked. If time constraints are respected, the procedure is considered completed, otherwise, the last node is removed and the constraints are checked again. This process is repeated until constraints are met or until only the seed node remains in the cluster.

A. Cluster Strategy

In this section the first phase of the heuristic method is described by the following algorithm.

Phase 1: Cluster Strategy.

Step 0. Initialization.

Set $\mathcal{K}^{\mathcal{N}^U} = \mathcal{K}$, $\mathcal{K}^U = \emptyset$, $\mathcal{N}^S = \emptyset$, $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$, $P^k = 0$, $k = 0$.

Step 1. New trip.

set $k = k + 1$

If $k \leq K$ **then**

set $m = 1$

else go to Step 9

End

Step 2. The choice of EV

Select $k \in \mathcal{K}^{\mathcal{N}^U}$ s.t. $C^k = \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}^{\mathcal{N}^U}} C^k$

Step 3. Determining the seed of the cluster

Let $n_f \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ be the farthest node from depot node n_0 not yet served neither included in any cluster.

Select $n_f \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ s.t. $Ttd_{0f}^k = \max_{j: (n_j \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S})} \{Ttd_{0j}^k\}$

If $\{(Q^k - c_{0j}^k - c_{jU}^k) > Q_L^k\}$ **then**

set $\mathcal{N}_m^k = \{n_f\}$

else set $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} \setminus \{n_f\}$ **and**

If $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \emptyset$ **go to Step 9.**

else go to Step 3.

End if

End if

Step 4. Populate the cluster following the nearest node criterion

Let $n_n \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ be the nearest not served node to the seed n_f .

Select $n_n \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} \setminus \mathcal{N}_m^k$ s.t.

$Ttd_{fn}^k = \min_{j: (n_j \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S})} \{Ttd_{fj}^k\}$

If $\{Q_i^k - c_{fj}^k \leq 0\}$ **then**

call SEARCH_CP_AND_CHARGE

else

If $\{(n_n \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}') \wedge (ed_p > 0.8 \cdot emax_p) \wedge$

$\wedge (Q_i^k > 0.70 \cdot Q^k) \wedge (P^k = p \vee P^k = 0)\}$ **then**

set $ed_p = ed_p - 0.10 \cdot Q_i^k$

set $Q_i^k = Q_i^k - 0.10 \cdot Q_i^k$

If $P^k = 0$

set $P^k = p$

End If

End if

Step 5. EV capacity constraints

Let check if node demand of products d_n and cluster demand L_m^k do not exceed the cargo capacity C^k of EV

$k \in \mathcal{K}$ trip.

If $\{d_n + L_m^k \leq C^k\}$ **then**
set $\mathcal{N}_m^k = \mathcal{N}_m^k \cup \{n_n\}$ **and go to Step 4.**
End if

SEARCH_CP_AND_CHARGE:

Search for the nearest CP $n_n \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}$.

Select $n_n \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}' \setminus \mathcal{N}_m^k$ s.t. $Ttd_{fn}^k = \min_{j:(n_j \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S})} \{d_{nj}^k\}$
If $\{Q_n^k - c_{nj}^k > 0\} \wedge (P^k = p \vee P^k = 0)$ **then**
 Let charge the EV with control of
 CP power peak and district power peak.
If $\{e_n \leq \text{emax}_n \wedge ed_p \leq \text{emax}_p\}$ **then**
Set $Q_n^k = Q_n^k + c_{nU}^k$
Set $P^k = p$
If $\{ed_p > (0.8 \cdot \text{emax}_p) \vee e_n > (0.8 \cdot \text{emax}_n)\}$
then
set $cost = cost_{c1} \cdot (Q^k - Q_n^k)$
else set $cost = cost_{c2} \cdot (Q^k - Q_n^k)$
End if
else set $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} \setminus \{n_n\}$
If $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \emptyset$ **go to Step 9.**
else restart the SEARCH_CP_AND_CHARGE

procedure.

End if

End if

else set $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} \setminus \{n_n\}$

If $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \emptyset$ **go to Step 9.**

else restart the SEARCH_CP_AND_CHARGE

procedure.

End if

End if

In Phase 1, the *Cluster Strategy* takes place. At *Step 0* k , P^k and the sets $\mathcal{K}^{\mathcal{N}^U}$, \mathcal{K}^U , \mathcal{N}^S , $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ are initialized. Then, if $k \leq K$, at *Step 1* the route m starts.

At *Step 2* the EVs are assigned to the clusters on the basis of their cargo capacity (assigned in descending order of cargo capacity). After that, at *Step 3* the seed node of the cluster is determined, choosing the farthest node from depot node not yet served neither included in any cluster. The algorithm checks that the EV can travel without the recharge need from the depot node to the seed and then to the final node. If the EV cannot complete the shortest trip with the current SoC, the seed node is removed from the set of not served nodes $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ and *Step 3* is repeated again. If $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ set is empty, it goes to *Step 9* and ends.

At *Step 4* the cluster is populated following the nearest node criterion. The nearest node to the seed not yet served ($n_n \in \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$) is selected. Then, in case the current battery SoC is not enough to reach that node n_n , the SEARCH_CP_AND_CHARGE procedure is called. The procedure searches the nearest CP to the seed and, if the CP node can be reached and the energy bounds of both CP and district are respected, the EV battery is charged, calculating the cost of charging. If the provided CP energy is $ed_p > (0.8 \cdot \text{emax}_p) \vee e_n > (0.8 \cdot \text{emax}_n)$, the energy cost is $cost_{c1}$, otherwise the cost is $cost_{c2}$.

If the SoC does not allow to reach the CP node n_n or the energy peak constraints are not verified, the algorithm updates the set of not served node $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ by deleting node n_n and in case the set $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ is not empty, it restarts the SEARCH_CP_AND_CHARGE procedure. In case $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S}$ is empty the algorithm goes to *Step 9* and ends. If the current SoC allows to reach the node $n_n \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$, and $n_n \in \hat{\mathcal{N}} \cup \mathcal{N}'$ then the district energy peak ed_p is checked. If ed_p is greater than 80% of emax_p and the SoC Q_n^k is greater than 70%, then the 10% of the current energy in battery is discharged and supplied back to the node n_n grid (V2G). Finally, at *Step 5*, we check if node products demand d_n and cluster products demand L_m^k do not exceed the cargo capacity C^k of EV $k \in \mathcal{K}$. If it is verified, the node n_n is added to the cluster and the algorithm goes to *Step 4*, otherwise *Phase 1* is concluded.

B. Routing Strategy

Once the cluster nodes are obtained, the *Routing Strategy* is carried out in Phase 2, as described by the following algorithm.

Phase 2: Routing Strategy.

Step 6. EVRP solution considering cluster nodes.

Set $\bar{j} = \lfloor \tilde{N}_m^k \rfloor + 2$.

Select $\tilde{N}_m^k(1)$ and $\tilde{N}_m^k(\bar{j})$.

Determine $\tilde{N}_m^k(2), \dots, \tilde{N}_m^k(\bar{j} - 1)$.

Determine B_m^k .

Step 7. Travel time constraints are checked.

Determine \hat{B}^k

If $\{B_m^k > T_r \vee \hat{B}^k > T_w\}$ **then**

The last node will be removed.

select $n_n \in \mathcal{N}_m^k$ s.t. $n_n = \max_{j:(n_j \in \mathcal{N}_m^k)} Ttd_{fn}^k$

set $\mathcal{N}_m^k = \mathcal{N}_m^k - \{n_n\}$ **and go to Step 6.**

End if.

Step 8. Checking EV trip closure conditions.

Set $\mathcal{N}^S = \mathcal{N}^S \cup \mathcal{N}_m^k$

set $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} \setminus \mathcal{N}_m^k$

If $\mathcal{N}^{\mathcal{N}^S} = \emptyset$ **then**

go to Step 9.

End if.

If $\{N_m^k = 0 \vee m \geq M - 1\}$ **then**

If $\mathcal{K}^{\mathcal{N}^U} \neq \emptyset$ **then**

set $\mathcal{K}^{\mathcal{N}^U} = \mathcal{K}^{\mathcal{N}^U} \setminus \{k\}$

set $\mathcal{K}^U = \mathcal{K}^U \cup \{k\}$

and go to Step 9.

End if

else set $m = m + 1$ **and go to Step 3.**

End if.

Step 9. END

In Phase 2, *Routing Strategy* is performed based on the cluster nodes found in Phase 1. At *Step 6* **the EVRP solution is searched** considering cluster nodes and starting and ending nodes according to [1]. At *Step 7* the time constraints fulfillment is checked. If time constraints are not verified, the node n_n is removed and the *Step 6* is repeated. After that, at *Step 8* the EV trip closure conditions are checked and at *Step 9*, Phase 2 and the heuristic algorithm are closed.

VI. POSTAL DELIVERY CASE STUDY

A. Comparison between MILP formulation and heuristic algorithm

In order to validate the heuristic algorithm, a study has been carried out by a set of instances and the results obtained from both the MILP problem and the heuristic algorithm have been compared. Table I describes the characteristics of the EVs that have been considered for the comparison between the MILP problem and the heuristics. Table I indicates the cargo capacity C^k , the battery capacity Q^k and consumption per 100 km traveled c_k of the EVs. A fleet of EVs with cargo capacities of 80 and 70 kg is considered. Based on battery capacity, these EVs are considered of small (40kWh) and medium (50kWh) type.

TABLE I
POSTAL DELIVERY EV CHARACTERISTICS

EV type	Number of EVs	C^k [Kg]	Q^k [kWh]	c_k [kWh/100km]
1	10	80	50	14.36
2	10	70	40	14.26

Table II shows the total number of nodes of each set used on the application of the optimization model and heuristic algorithm. We consider a total number of six sets and for each set, five different instances are considered. In each instance of the same set the number of nodes and the characteristics of the EVs remain unchanged. On the contrary, in each instance there are some characteristics of the nodes that are randomly varied: 1) the customers demand d_i , 2) the opening hour $open_i$ to start the service allowed at node n_i , and 3) the closing hour $close_i$ to finish the service at node n_i . Each instance of the set is represented by a number with format $x.y$, where x identifies the set and y identifies the instance of the set, as reported in Table III).

TABLE II
DATA SETS CHARACTERISTICS

Sets	Number of nodes
1	27
2	29
3	34
4	38
5	40
6	42

Table III shows the results obtained by the application of the optimization model and the heuristic algorithm. The solution has been obtained with a CPU Intel I7 3.4 GHz and a RAM of 16GB. More precisely, the MILP solution is obtained by CPLEX and the heuristic algorithm is implemented in Apache Netbeans IDE 14. The results show the total distance (in km) OPT and the CPU time of the optimization problem (CPU OPT), and the total distance (in km) HEU and the CPU time of the heuristic algorithm (CPU HEU). To assess the effectiveness of heuristics, the optimality gap is calculated taking into account the value of the objective function in

the optimization (second column) and the heuristic (fourth column) models. The optimality gap is defined as follows:

$$Gap = (HEU - OPT)/OPT \cdot 100. \quad (63)$$

TABLE III
POSTAL DELIVERY COMPARISON BETWEEN MILP PROBLEM AND HEURISTIC ALGORITHM

Instance	CPU OPT [ms]	OPT [km]	CPU HEU [ms]	HEU [km]	GAP [%]
1.1	253	1384.68	176	1397.41	0.92
1.2	497	1372.34	161	1385.08	0.92
1.3	501	1384.68	160	1397.41	0.92
1.4	597	1372.345	192	1385.08	0.93
1.5	496	1372.345	165	1385.08	0.92
2.1	268	1259.26	184	1270.04	0.86
2.2	4676	1209.58	187	1220.73	0.92
2.3	6112	1386.257	194	1401.637	1.11
2.4	40194	1373.92	183	1389.3	1.12
2.5	6216	1375.85	195	1382.74	0.5
3.1	251	1127.56	183	1136.5	0.79
3.2	2243	1156.79	180	1160.81	0.35
3.3	20975	1279.6	212	1284.24	0.36
3.4	24884	1173.1	227	1185.852	1.09
3.5	1985	1458.11	213	1462.38	0.29
4.1	1810	1612.69	288	1616.14	0.21
4.2	4600	1243.69	261	1251.19	0.6
4.3	232105	1277.67	255	1282.3	0.36
4.4	239645	1469.39	235	1484.89	1.06
4.5	38981	1634.27	282	1637.98	0.23
5.1	555	1351.4	329	1355.53	0.31
5.2	492897	1476.71	306	1489.01	0.83
5.3	54892	1496.51	252	1512.3	1.06
5.4	70360	1690.16	252	1705.79	0.92
5.5	610	1125.1	190	1129.38	0.38
6.1	267	1444.26	256	1449.79	0.38
6.2	4267	1137.06	236	1141.71	0.42
6.3	36073	1275.34	216	1288.57	1.04
6.4	434862	1276.79	215	1290.02	1.04
6.5	700	1187.42	225	1191.9	0.38

We note that the Gap average value over 30 instances is 0.7%. This consistency is quite remarkable. Furthermore, the algorithm only exhibits a maximum Gap value of 1.12%, which demonstrates its robustness and efficiency. In light of these results, we can confidently assert that the heuristic algorithm is not only highly effective but also capable of tackling more complex problems that necessitate longer execution times.

B. Postal Delivery Case Study Description

This section explains in more detail the case study focused on PD activity in the province of the city of Bari (Italy). The case study considers 41 customer nodes, 21 CPs, 7 of them are also considered customer nodes, and one Depot node used as start and end node. The distribution of the nodes in the network is shown on Fig. 1.

All nodes are connected to each other by bidirectional arcs. In Table IV the EVs data are reported. In particular, a heterogeneous fleet of EVs is considered and based on battery capacity, the EVs are considered of medium (70kWh) and large (107.8kWh) type.

By the application of heuristic algorithm, in Table V the route defined for each EV is described. In this case, EV 1-5

Fig. 1. Nodes Distribution Postal Delivery Case Study.

TABLE IV
POSTAL DELIVERY EVS DATA

EV type	Number of EVs	C^k [kg]	Q^k [kWh]	c_k [kWh/100km]
1	5	90	70	12.36
2	10	100	70	14.26
3	5	150	107.8	14.36

are considered of type 3, EV 6-10 are of type 1, and EV 11-13 are of type 2.

TABLE V
POSTAL DELIVERY EVS ROUTES

EV k	EV type	\tilde{N}_m^k
1	3	$n_0, n_{45}, n_{44}, n_{43}, n_0$
2	3	$n_0, n_{40}, n_{41}, n_{42}, n_{47}, n_0$
3	3	$n_0, n_{49}, n_{48}, n_{46}, n_0$
4	3	$n_0, n_{63}, n_{56}, n_{55}, n_0$
5	3	$n_0, n_6, n_4, n_{11}, n_{62}, n_{27}, n_{28}, n_{29}, n_{30}, n_{31}, n_{35}, n_{32}, n_{34}, n_{33}, n_{26}, n_3, n_0$
6	1	$n_0, n_{19}, n_{39}, n_{14}, n_{38}, n_{20}, n_0$
7	1	n_0, n_{58}, n_{57}, n_0
8	1	n_0, n_{15}, n_0
9	1	n_0, n_{54}, n_0
10	1	$n_0, n_7, n_2, n_{61}, n_{60}, n_{23}, n_{21}, n_{18}, n_{53}, n_{50}, n_{51}, n_9, n_8, n_{16}, n_1, n_0$
11	2	n_0, n_{24}, n_0
12	2	$n_0, n_{37}, n_{12}, n_{13}, n_0$
13	2	n_0, n_{36}, n_0

Table VI indicates the duration of the EV trip (B_m^k), the total traveled length [km], the total cargo load of the cluster, the total travel cost, and the CP used in case of EV charge or discharge energy. In this case study it is considered $cost_{c1} = 0.35[\text{€} \setminus kWh]$ and $cost_{c2} = cost_d = 0.25[\text{€} \setminus kWh]$.

From these results, it is interesting to note that EV k_{10} uses CP n_{51} to charge battery and node n_{51} belongs to district 6. Also node n_{45} belongs to district 6, used by EV k_1 to discharge the battery. In this case, it can be observed how EV k_1 has plenty of energy to reach the Depot. That is why, in order to not overload the main grid, EV k_1 provides energy back at CP node n_{45} to allow k_{10} to charge so that it can reach its destination by respecting the constraints.

The EVs k_5 and k_{10} are the ones that take the longest time

TABLE VI
POSTAL DELIVERY EVS ROUTE RESULTS

EV k	B_1^k [min]	Length [km]	L^k [kg]	SoC at n_U [kWh]	T.t. cost [€]	CP used n_i
1	256	380	8	43.27	-9.74	n_{45}
2	250	341	20	49.88	0	-
3	230	323	15	52.96	0	-
4	186	301	10	56.8	0	-
5	304	458	58	29.87	0	-
6	214	288	26	28.05	0	-
7	172	256	3	32.6	0	-
8	138	200	8	40.75	0	-
9	134	198	2	41.13	0	-
10	259	377	85	20.96	+19.48	n_{51}
11	130	187	8	38.51	0	-
12	140	189	20	38.1	0	-
13	87	114	7	50.78	0	-

to complete the route. This is because their route includes a high number of clients. Travel time, delivery time, and, in the case of EV k_{10} , battery charging time are taken into account. Moreover, because of the number of served nodes, k_5 and k_{10} are also the two EVs with the highest total cargo load.

On the contrary, EV k_{13} is the one with the shortest path and that's why it takes the shortest time to complete the delivery activity.

Fig. 2. Route Postal Delivery Case Study.

Not served customer nodes are those with $d_i = 0$ or unreachable in terms of battery capacity. Figure 2 shows the resulting route of each EV following the visit order of the nodes, based on Figure 1 network.

VII. WASTE COLLECTION CASE STUDY

A. Comparison between MILP formulation and heuristic algorithm

In this section, the mathematical MILP model is compared with the heuristic algorithm. In this way, the effectiveness of the heuristic that allows us to solve more complex problems is verified. Table VII describes the characteristics of the EVs that have been considered in the Waste Collection case to compare MILP problem and heuristic algorithm. Table VII indicates the cargo capacity of each EV C^k , the battery capacity Q^k and

consumption per 100 km traveled c_k . It is considered a fleet of EVs with cargo capacity of 70 and 80 kg. Based on battery capacity, these EVs are considered of medium (50) and small (40) type.

TABLE VII
WASTE COLLECTION EV CHARACTERISTICS

EV type	Number of EVs	C^k [kg]	Q^k [kWh]	c_k [kWh/100km]
1	10	80	50	14.36
2	10	70	40	14.26

Table VIII describes the data sets characteristics of WC activity used on the application of the optimization model and heuristic algorithm. We consider a total number of eight sets and, for each set, five different instances are considered. In each instance of the same set the number of nodes and the characteristics of the EVs remain unchanged. On the contrary, in each instance there are some characteristics of the nodes that are randomly variated: 1) the customers demand d_i , 2) the opening hour $open_i$ to start the service allowed at node n_i , and 3) the closing hour $close_i$ to finish the service at node n_i . Each instance of the set is represented by a number with format $x.y$, where x identifies the set and y identifies the instance of the set, as reported in Table IX.

TABLE VIII
DATA SETS CHARACTERISTICS

Sets	Number of nodes
1	27
2	29
3	34
4	38
5	40
6	42
7	45
8	50

Table IX shows the results obtained by the application of the MILP optimization model and the heuristic algorithm. The solution has been obtained with a CPU Intel I7 3.4 GHz and a RAM of 16GB. The results obtained show the total distance (in km) OPT and the CPU time for the optimization problem (CPU OPT), and the total distance (in km) HEU and the CPU time for the heuristic algorithm (CPU HEU). Also in this case to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of the heuristics and extend the analysis to encompass significantly larger and more realistic scenarios, we employ the optimality gap.

The obtained results indicate that, when considering the average performance across multiple instances, the algorithm exhibits a gap of 7.86%. This gap represents the difference between the solutions generated by the algorithm and the known optimal solutions. The fact that this average gap is relatively small, at 7.86%, suggests that the algorithm generally performs quite well. In most of the cases or instances tested, the algorithm is successful in producing solutions that are very close to the optimal ones. The overall performance of the algorithm appears to be satisfactory.

TABLE IX
WASTE COLLECTION COMPARISON BETWEEN MILP PROBLEM AND HEURISTIC ALGORITHM

Instance	CPU OPT [ms]	OPT [km]	CPU HEU [ms]	HEU [km]	GAP [%]
1.1	594	1,80	379	2,05	13,98
1.2	406	1,64	300	1,80	9,94
1.3	456	1,64	328	1,80	9,53
1.4	485	1,80	422	1,84	2,53
1.5	452	1,68	333	1,80	7,17
2.1	437	1,74	427	1,82	4,88
2.2	1331	1,41	361	1,80	27,56
2.3	1378	1,66	423	1,80	8,49
2.4	1352	1,42	512	1,80	26,97
2.5	398	1,69	513	1,82	8,02
3.1	655	1,91	626	2,02	5,64
3.2	13754	1,76	614	2,03	15,37
3.3	13484	1,76	626	1,94	10,35
3.4	13601	1,64	781	1,76	7,93
3.5	14380	1,76	565	1,99	13,28
4.1	2510	1,81	815	1,96	8,21
4.2	34259	1,81	799	1,89	4,20
4.3	145334	1,91	813	1,98	3,68
4.4	147892	1,84	790	1,91	3,72
4.5	142596	1,84	780	1,98	7,47
5.1	1040	1,81	849	1,86	3,24
5.2	175922	1,74	712	1,74	0,11
5.3	21266	1,82	973	1,83	0,20
5.4	227322	1,78	975	1,91	6,88
5.5	1094	1,80	894	1,88	4,79
6.1	1045	1,73	902	1,80	4,15
6.2	18982	1,82	838	2,04	12,22
6.3	21124	1,75	1,033	1,91	9,52
6.4	220179	1,78	757	1,86	4,56
6.5	3827	1,76	934	1,80	2,48
7.1	892	1,66	957	1,71	2,88
7.2	3757	1,64	1,116	1,65	0,47
7.3	20085	1,57	860	1,73	10,50
7.4	218486	1,79	895	2,04	13,77
7.5	1203	1,62	909	1,71	5,89
8.1	1577	1,84	1,368	1,91	3,71
8.2	3728	2,01	1,319	2,14	6,25
8.3	555138	1,87	1,115	2,15	15,25
8.4	1955,236	1,96	1,209	2,13	8,79
8.5	21702	2,07	1,250	2,07	0,08

B. Waste Collection Case Study Description

This section explains in more detail the case study focused on WC activity in the province of Bari city (Italy). The case study consider 1100 customer nodes, 400 CPs, 50 of them are considered also customer nodes, one depot node used as start node, and one end node. CPs are distributed in Y=8 districts.

TABLE X
WASTE COLLECTION EVs DATA

EV type	Number of EVs	C^k [kg]	Q^k [kWh]	c_k [kWh/100km]
1	10	150	90.6	14.36
2	10	200	107.8	14.26

It holds $cost_{e1} = 0.35[€/kWh]$ and $cost_{e2} = cost_d = 0.25[€/kWh]$. In Table X, the EVs data are reported. The fleet is formed by two types of EVs considered large type due to the battery capacity. There are 10 EVs of each type. EV1

type has 150 kg cargo capacity and *EV2* has 200 kg cargo capacity.

C. Waste Collection Results

In this section, results of WC case study are presented. From the solution obtained by applying the heuristic algorithm shown in Table XI, it can be seen how 45 routes are distributed in 18 trips. Table XI gives the solution of the Waste Collection case study. During the trip, the EV can carry out the routes taking into account the maximum time of both EV route and trip: $T_r = 270$ [minutes] and $T_w = 480$ [minutes]. EVs trip starts from the depot node with fully charged battery. However, before returning to the depot, they can carry out several routes and, when finished, they return to the depot node empty. 45 routes are needed to carry out the activity divided into 18 trips. By analyzing the results obtained by the heuristic approach, we can deduce that, despite the large number of trips to carry out the waste collection activity, the solution is obtained in reasonable time by respecting the constraints. Moreover, the power grid requirements are as well respected. Some EVs discharge their batteries feeding back energy into the grid, in order to allow other EVs to charge and finish the route without reaching the energy peak both at CP and district level.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the Electric Vehicle Routing Problem (EVRP) specified for Postal Delivery (PD) and Waste Collection (WC) activities. The main objective is to minimize the route length of EVs taking into account the EV battery and power grid requirements. Smart charging is applied, in which EV batteries can be charged or discharged to not exceed the energy peaks both at Charge Point (CP) and district level.

The PD and WC problems are modeled and solved as Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problems. To address the problem complexity and deal with large systems, two heuristic algorithms are presented for solving both PD and WC problems and are compared with MILP models. For the comparison, two case studies are analyzed, respectively for the PD and WC problems.

In the case of PD, a heterogeneous fleet of small and medium-sized EVs is considered and the distance travelled along the route is minimized, charging or discharging energy when needed. The power grid is never overloaded, and the established peak energy limits are respected.

In the case of WC, the fleet is also heterogeneous but, in this case, it is considered composed by large-size EVs. In this case, the number of nodes is much higher, also achieving the minimization of the route of each one of the EVs, respecting the battery level and the power grid requirements. The resulting optimality gaps demonstrate that the heuristic algorithms can be successfully used in large scale problems.

Future works will address the EVRP problems in more realistic contexts considering traffic conditions and dynamic routing to modify in real time the route planning by using information and communication technologies.

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TABLE XI
WASTE COLLECTION RESULTS

Electric Vehicle k	EV type	route duration [min]	length [km]	T.t cost [€]
1	2	23 64 119 80	12,4 10 2 15	0
2	2	68 32 32 32 14 124	42 8 8 6 5 21	0
3	2	54 54 9 35 131	40 10 6 10 21	0
4	2	57 9 128 40 30	33 6 27 14 8	0
5	2	96 74 138	40 14 25	0
6	2	20 142 85 12	10 26 21 9	28.14
7	2	108 25 171	37 10 24	28.33
8	2	39 39 28 45 93	24 13 12 17 22	0
9	2	129 65 113	38 17 25	33.87
10	2	135 29 129	41 12 25	28.57
11	1	50 60 15 165	24 21 11 27	-45.30
12	1	37 315	23 77	0
13	1	37 194 26 35	22 33 13 15	-22.65
14	1	42 31 30 91 69	21 15 14 21 19	-22.70
15	1	318 18	66 12	0
16	1	32 238 15	18 47 11	-22.65
17	1	39 17 21 215	19 12 12 47	-22.65
18	1	261	56	-22.65